

Annual Highlights

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A year in review

We're proud to share our 2024 highlights with our global community! It's been a year of steady growth and progress as we continue to champion equitable open access publishing, raise the profile of trustworthy OA journals, and strengthen our organisation.

Equity and diversity are at the core of DOAJ. Our [Ambassador Programme](#) has worked with journal editors and publishers worldwide to raise awareness of OA and advocate for best practices. In 2024, we [reviewed the programme](#), ensuring it aligns with [our mission](#) and supports our globally distributed organisation. The review highlighted the programme's positive impact and provided recommendations to enhance how we support the network, which we're excited to implement in 2025.

We've also collaborated on more equitable business models at European and global levels, for example, through the [CRAFT-OA](#) and [DIAMAS](#) Horizon Europe projects and with AJOL, EIFL and WACREN's [project in Africa](#), reflecting our commitment to community-driven, fee-free publishing models that ensure equitable access to knowledge.

This year, we were especially pleased to expand our outreach in Africa and Latin America, hosting [a multilingual webinar series](#) to strengthen regional journals and improve the visibility of regional research.

All DOAJ-indexed journals meet [our rigorous quality criteria](#), the gold standard in open access publishing. During 2024's widespread concern about trust and standards in scholarly publishing, we've increased transparency about the [people](#) and [processes](#) involved in keeping questionable practices out of the index, enhancing the trust of our indexed journals.

We remain focused on sustainability, resilience and transparency. We conducted [a community consultation](#) on how our metadata is used to guide our future priorities and ensure our services remain relevant and useful. We also published [our strategic roadmap](#) online.

We're excited for 2025 and to continue leading in the evolving global open access landscape. We are committed to fostering a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable future for open access publishing. Our achievements represent the efforts of not only DOAJ's core team but also our 100+ volunteer editors and ambassadors and the wider DOAJ family—publishers, researchers, libraries, funders and partners—who support our work. We are grateful to them all and look forward to continuing this journey together.

— **Joanna Ball**, Managing Director DOAJ

DOAJ highlights 2024

21,300 Journals indexed

136 Countries represented

89 Languages represented

Map representing publisher countries of journals indexed in DOAJ

28.13 million pageviews from **13.3** million unique visitors

7.7 million clicks on links

2.71 million hits to our [journals search page](#)

698 million hits to our API

The year in numbers

In 2024, we had:

8,298 Applications received

3,860 Update requests received

1,901 Applications accepted

22.9% of Applications accepted

13 Editorial Staff

113 Volunteer and Associate editors

Another busy year for the Editorial team, **adding nearly 2,000 journals to DOAJ**, as well as updating many others, and providing publishers with support and advice on open access best practices. We welcomed a **new Managing Editor** in Indonesia to the team. We also focussed on **strengthening our quality criteria** and processes, and committed more hours than ever **to ensuring predatory publishers are not included in DOAJ**.

— **Judith Barnsby**, Head of Editorial

Trust

In 2024, expanding on the theme of Trust, we published **four series of blog posts** centred on transparency and trust:

- **Journal stories**
- **Meet the team**
- **Volunteer highlights**
- **Meet our Ambassadors**

Meet the DOAJ team:

DOAJ Volunteers

In 2024, the DOAJ Quality Team (six Managing Editors) conducted 473 investigations, dedicating 837 hours to strengthening the trust in our index — our most extensive effort to date!

We refined our methods and processes to identify and investigate suspicious journals more efficiently. 70% of the investigations led to embargoes of at least one year, effectively preventing these journals from being indexed.

Ambassador programme

In 2024 we reviewed the Ambassador programme and:

The programme will continue with a refocus on low- and middle-income countries.

We strengthened the organisational and management structure, and clarified roles and responsibilities.

We will provide comprehensive and continuous training resources to equip Ambassadors with the tools and knowledge to perform their roles.

We will recruit new Ambassadors for Africa, Brazil, and Ukraine.

“DOAJ's mission to advance open access to quality scholarly journals across all regions motivating me to become an Ambassador. I admired and continue to appreciate DOAJ's commitment to inclusivity and avoidance of reliance on impact factors.” — **Ina Smith, DOAJ Senior Ambassador**

“The DOAJ has established criteria for indexing journals. Support from Ambassadors could be useful in my region in understanding these criteria and communicating them effectively to researchers and publishers.” — **Amber Osman, DOAJ Ambassador**

Project highlights

Community consultation

We commissioned a community **survey that received 1,690 responses** from around the globe. The data is helping us determine our future direction and ensuring we meet our communities' diverse needs.

Research4Life | DOAJ | ASSAF Accredited Publisher Course

We collaborated with Research4Life and ASSAf to put on a **four-module course in English, Spanish, French, and Ukrainian**. The aim was to cover Research4Life countries in Africa and Latin America and to offer courses to Ukraine.

In total, **983 participants from 53 countries** attended the webinars. Most participants expressed that the event was engaging and appreciated the hands-on nature of the sessions.

Project highlights

Metadata accuracy and recency

We developed **new tools and processes** to help us improve the accuracy and recency of our journal metadata. For example, an automated link checker checks links in applications in real time and validates answers.

Supporting equitable models for open access publishing

We have **collaborated with European partners to build capacity, tools, quality and sustainability** for institutionally-published journals through the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects, and highlighted diamond journals from Australia, Colombia, and Brazil as part of [our journal stories blog series](#).

We know librarians play an important role in supporting journals with the indexing process, and we have collaborated with organisations like LIBER to help them with this.

**Thank you for
using
promoting
supporting
applying to
advocating for
contributing to
teaching others about**

